

THE MAIN PROBLEMS OF THE INTRODUCTION OF IFRS INTO THE DOMESTIC PRACTICE OF ACCOUNTING AND REPORTING

Sheralieva Elnora Abdusaitovna

master's student,

Tashkent Financial University, Uzbekistan

**Supervisor— Candidate of Economic Sciences,
Associate Professor F.Qilicheva**

Abstract: In this article, the author examines the problems associated with the introduction of international financial reporting standards into the accounting system of Uzbekistan, suggests ways to solve them and describes the main advantages of their adoption.

Keywords: International Financial Reporting Standards, reporting, balance sheet.

First of all, it is worth noting the point in the formation of IFRS in Uzbekistan Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 4611 dated February 24, 2021 On Additional measures for the Transition to International Financial Reporting Standards. It can be stated that the application of IFRS in Uzbekistan today is more declared than actually implemented in practice. This situation is mainly due to the fact that IFRS requires reliable market estimates and the reflection of assets and liabilities. Let us consider in more detail what is the essence of the above-mentioned practical difficulties of applying IFRS in Uzbekistan. The absence of an established market economy in Uzbekistan today is evidenced by the difficulties in obtaining reliable market estimates:

- current market or replacement value in the absence of an active market for the relevant goods and services;

- the possible selling price in the absence of an active market for the relevant goods and services;
- discounted or present value due to an unbiased market interest rate in the amount of the refinancing rate established by the National Bank of the Republic of Belarus;
- current market value in the presence of an active market of goods and services;
- fair value due to the lack of sufficiently qualified and experienced appraisers.

In the context of the development of the new economy of the Republic of Belarus, both information users and their needs are radically changing, and the financial statements of companies must evolve to meet these changes [1].

It should also be noted here that the application of IFRS implies a special mindset. When preparing IFRS financial statements, it is necessary to shift the emphasis from instructions and regulations to the formation of professional thinking, the accountant's judgment. Serious difficulties will arise with the timeliness of obtaining official texts of standards and the quality of translation. In order to apply the IFRS standards in Belarus, it is required not just their official translation into the state language (Russian or Belarusian), but the creation of a permanent system for translating the texts of standards and interpretations in connection with regular changes made to them by the IFRS Council. As for the quality of translation, foreign experience shows that the content of standards is often incorrect, since certain concepts are not used in the legislation of some countries and it is impossible to find adequate terms for them [2].

Reforming accounting in the direction of convergence with IFRS will require the implementation of a set of measures to improve basic professional accounting

education, the creation of appropriate educational and methodological support, retraining of teachers, etc. The experience of other countries is interesting in this regard. A new educational standard of higher professional education in the specialty "Accounting, analysis and audit" has been developed and implemented in Russia, which, according to experts, including foreign, corresponds to international educational programs for the training of accountants. With the introduction of the Egyptian Accounting Standards based on IFRS in 2006, Cairo University began training specialists to take exams for obtaining an international certificate [3].

The introduction of IFRS into domestic accounting practice will lead to the need to strengthen state supervision over their compliance. This will require the adoption of amendments and additions to the Law "On Auditing Activities", providing for the conduct of audits in accordance with International Auditing Standards, and the creation of a special supervisory authority following the example of other states. For example, a Securities Commission regulatory monitoring office has been established in Pakistan, a Capital Markets Council in Turkey, and a Financial Supervision Agency in Kazakhstan. In some countries, stock exchanges monitor the quality of IFRS reporting. For example, the department for admission to trading and the Sanctions Commission of the Swiss Exchange SWX applies sanctions against issuers of securities in case of non-compliance with financial reporting requirements. It is obvious that the transition of the national accounting system to IFRS will entail significant costs both at the state level (for the official translation of standards, the creation of an infrastructure for the application of IFRS, the transformation of the system of regulation and control of accounting and reporting, training and advanced training of personnel) and in individual organizations (for the replacement or modernization of software, staff training, audit and consulting services). For example, the budget for the implementation of IFRS in

Macedonia amounted to EUR 7.36 million. According to the Institute of Chartered Accountants of England and Wales, in companies listing securities on the markets of the European Union, the cost of implementing IFRS is on average from 0.5 million EUR to 3.4 million EUR. A real help could be the creation of a specialized body at the state level in the Republic of Belarus — responsible coordinator of the process of transition to IFRS, as well as the formation of specialized departments on the basis of state executive authorities, whose responsibilities should include the study and analysis of the experience of implementing IFRS, the development of draft regulations on accounting, financial and management accounting in accordance with international experience, as well as the performance of some functions of control over financial accounting and financial reporting under IFRS [4].

Prospects and options for transition to IFRS:

- adoption of international standards as they are;
- adoption of IFRS with the possibility of their "limited modification";
- Development of national financial reporting standards through their maximum possible harmonization with IFRS. Real benefits from the introduction of IFRS in Belarus:

- growth of market capitalization;
- access to foreign capital markets and reduction of the price of attracted capital;
- inflow of foreign investments into the economy;
- greater transparency of domestic companies and, as a result, improved business image abroad;
- deeper integration of the country's economy into the world economic system, etc.

Reference

1. Панков, Д. Трудности перехода: законы, кадры, расходы / Д.Панков, Т. Рыбак // Экономическая газета [Электронный ресурс]. — 2009. — Режим доступа: http://www.neg.by/publication/2009_07_17_11693.html?print=1. — Дата доступа: 01.04.2015. 31
2. Дубинина, Н. Проблемы внедрения и эффективность применения Международных стандартов финансовой отчетности на предприятиях Республики Беларусь / Т. Дубинина // Бизнес.Online [Электронный ресурс]. — 2011. — Режим доступа: <http://msfo.bl.by/articles/71432.php> — Дата доступа: 27.03.2015.
3. Кожарская, Н. Проблемы перехода и перспективы внедрения МСФО в Республике Беларусь / Н. Кожарская // Бухгалтерский учет и анализ. — 2010. — №4. — С.27-31.
4. Murodovna, R. G. (2021). Analytical procedure in an audit of fixed assets. International Journal of Financial Management and Economics International Journal of Financial Management and Economics, 4(1), 41-45P.
5. Rahimova G. (2021). Accounting of the results of continuous revaluation of property, plant and equipment in accordance with international standards. Society and innovations, (Общество и инновации) (Жамият ва ва инновациялар) 3(2021) / ISSN 2181-1415.
6. Rakhimova G. (2021). The main instrument of calculation is the theoretical justification of the stratification of flour into the current state and people's standards./ International multidisciplinary scientific conferences on the DIALOGUE BETWEEN SCIENCE & ARTS, RELIGION/ 65-67 P.